

Morphological Analysis of Contai Town, East Midnapore, West Bengal, India

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ABSTRACT

Morphology of a town is concerned with the ground build and skyline of the houses . The plan may be internal which concerns with the arrangements of streets and built space or external which concerns with shape and the bird's eye view of the street patterns developed in a settlement. Morphological character is closely associated to functional character of a place .Morphology is not a matter of historical interest; there are trends in development leading from the past to present. The presumption is that trends obvious at the present time which have been established over the past, will be continued into the future unless positive action is taken to change them. This article made study of evolution of the cultural lands cape of contai town by a systematic investigation of its function. Morphology is dynamic .So morphology of contain town will never be static in future. So the main objective of this article is to shoe the formation of present and systematic development of the town in future and also giving an idea of the areal coverage of the open spaces and parks.

OBJECTIVES :-

- * To analyse present landscape formation of tours
- * To find out the reason for defection and characterization of change of landscape overtime.
- * To discuss the planning strategy for future development.
- * To detect the arising problem of city formation and find out remedy to overcome of it.

METHODOLOGY :- The whole information and data are collected from District census Handbook (1901, 2001) , non - governmental organization , B.L.R. office , land Registered office and detailed project report of Contai Municipality. At last conclusion and recommendation are prepared for overall development of the Contai town.

STUDY AREA :- Contai (also known as Kanthi) is head quarters of Contai subdivision in Purba Medinipur , west Bengal , India . Southern subdivision of the district lying between $21^{\circ}36'$ N and $22^{\circ}01'$ N and between $87^{\circ}25'$ E and $87^{\circ}59'$ E with an area of 819 square miles .The south east part is a maritime tract lying along the Bay of Bengal. The rest of the part is an alluvial plain watered by two navigable rivers, the Haldi and Rasulpur and by a number of tidal and khals, most of which fall into those two rivers.

INTRODUCTION :- Towns vary widely in their forms. They reflect the physical and cultural factors of the site and situation. A physical factor is not so important in determining the forms of town. The cultural factors, such as forts, old market place, roads, and administrative offices are more important in determining the form of the towns. The appraisal of the sky line of the buildings viewed from a vantage point situated either in the core or in the periphery reveals some interesting facts. The business area of the city is usually distinguished by multi-storyed buildings indicating there by a high density of population per house. The hotchpotch development of building is noticed which indicates the differential character of the city.

In the beginning of the formation of a city, some sets of centripetal forces originate after the formation of the main nucleus. The resultant outcome of the centripetal forces appears in the form of concentric development in the built up area. After this the role of another force ensues which attracts the establishments towards the peripheral zones. After the concentric development around nuclei the advent of roads and railways caused the sector type development in cities. The physical and cultural barriers such as steep slopes, rivers, have been responsible for such type of developments either along some roads or in some other elongated zones.

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS :- This town is a very old town and not growing planwise. So it has been growing unsystematically for which several problems like drainage and other problems are occurred. As it is situated on the sand dune, drainage problem of this municipality is now a burning problem. Like all other small and medium towns, the govt. Is not able to allot sufficient fund for the all round development of the town and also extend essential amenities to the weaker section of the people. This municipality was established in the year 1958 and consisting of 18 wards. Initially the

population if the area was 603,136 in 1901, as compared with 545,358 in 1891, the density being 710 persons to the square mile. It contains 2062 villages. Including Contai, this is the most progressive part of the Midnapore district, the population increasing by 10.6 percent during the decade ending in 1901, owing largely to the influx of cultivators to the newly reclaimed lands. There are 49 km bituminous and 78 km water bound macadam road in this town. The Railway station and central bus terminus are situated at the western side of the town. For which the town is expanding towards west rapidly and also socio-economical complexion is changing rapidly at that area. It is the gateway to Digha Behiri which is situated 6 km from this town is a historical places. The temple of goddess Sitala which is situated 6 km from this town is a historical places. The temple of goddess Sitala which is situated 8 km from this town is also a historical places. In the novel of Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyaya is also a place interest. Besides there junput, sea based fishing centre and sand dunes of Contai attract the visitors. Municipality could not create any housing facilities to the people of this town. Only housing facilities are given to the Harijan employees. Excepting that there are some Govt. Quarters are constructed for Govt. employees. Due to growth of population there is high demand for housing complexes. The better developed road sites are Digha road; Despriya Sasmal road, Gandhi road. Presently the town is expanding through the multi-nuclei developmental phase. In ward no 6, 9, 15 were settle by invading Muslims where they destroyed the Hindu structures of the area. Thus, urban growth in the multi-nucleus form is taking place and these peripheral developments, planned colonies are coming up because of the interest taken by the town and country planning departments for the regulated expansions.

The main business section of the town is found at the chowrongi. It is the oldest site. Its growth has been haphazard without any plan. On account of the transportation facilities, its main function is commercial. As is common to all indigeneous part of the Indian city it is highly populated and densely built. The streets are narrow and crooked. The houses are mostly two storied, mud-walled and tile roofed. Many modern building have been built along the road site. Most of the houses are used for commercial purposes – shops and storages. The residential houses are modern and metalled. All are situated all over the town but mostly along the road side.

SIZE :- The urban centres, however, can be classified into some general categories so far as the outer shapes and forms are concerned, which in themselves are the end product of the interplay of various physical and cultural factors, through different periods and cultural factors, through different periods of history. Many tons are related with variety shape like triangular, rectangular, elongated circular and amorphous. In each case the pattern is related to some dominant physical factors or cultural factors and as a result of mixture of both the factors.

Urban agglomerations cannot be reliably distinguished from rural agglomerations by size alone. An agglomeration may consist only a few hectares, or it may have inhabitants numbering in millions and be so extensive as to cover hundreds of square kilometers. But neither the number of people nor the areal extent are sure measures of the functions or the importance of the agglomeration. To be sure, rural agglomerations are usually smaller urban ones, and large centres are usually of more importance than small ones.

Many towns which do not conform to any geometrical pattern fall into amorphous shape category. Many smaller towns comply irregular shapes. Contai is one of them. The town is very old and not growing planwise. So it has been growing unsystematically. The unequal pull of various roads according to the commercial connection of the city with the surrounding areas, the position of the administrative section and the location of the market places are factors which appear to have contributed in varying degrees to the irregular form of town.

THE PRESENCE OF ROADS :- The road and street designs in the morphology played a very significant role, as the main cultural component .

In the process of the development, the development of buildings in a city, the roads function as the skeleton. The transportation is beyond doubt an integral thread of the urban fabric which in turn is highly governed by the system and pattern of the road net. The diffusing and concentrating elements of the road affect and sustain the location, growth and morphology of a town.

The development of roads is very much governed by the physical features of the landscape. Flat plains may increase the development of roads whereas the hindrances put forth by rough terrain, hillocks ranges and steep slopes might create a blockade in the further development of roads. The physical influence not only the degrees of development of roads but also the pattern and design.

As the town Contai are unplanned, there is not any definite street pattern. The town with pre-British origin which have grown at all during the last century shows a striking contrast between the indigenous part. The indigenous part have irregular street pattern which are widening by-lanes. The main roads are rarely more than 10 to 15 metres wide, often without side walls. Sometimes their width is less than 5 m with several bottlenecks causing. Consequently the chance erected buildings and roads of different nature provide a compact, congested and most irregular appearance in Contai town. The side street and alleys are usually much narrower and so crooked that wheeled cannot enter. The main road encroached upon by wooden structure shops whose roofs are projected on the road.

In Contai there are 49 km bituminous road, 78km water bound macadam road, 2 km cement concrete road. The link roads and lakes require immediate repairing due to growth of population widening of link roads and lakes are urgently require. Besides this one circular road is also require for easy movement of vehicle and passengers. The Gandhi road, Digha road, Netaji Sarani, Vidyasagar sarani, Bidhan Sarani – the minor roads are rectangular in form. In ward no – 16,1,2,8 the minor roads are triangular in form. In ward ni.9 some good residential houses have been built here the minor roads are in cobweb pattern, quadrangular roads are exists in North – western and middle parts of Contai town. In way to Mahisamundo, petua and Rasulpur the roads pattern are totally asymmetrical. The major streets are neither rectangular non circular, but in some cases they are straight lines. On the whole they are mostly irregular lines. Thus the present pattern of the road ways of the Contai town can be termed as irregular in form and lacks a definite system.

HOUSING PATTERN :- The housing pattern of Contai town is very well. The high rised building cover many parts of this town. More than town storied building predominate, although lofty building or three, four stories may exist along the main street. The common type of masonry construction are knows as pucca houses which are made up of brick, mortar and often covered with plastic and tile as roofing material. Kutcha houses with mudwall and tile roof or even thatch roof are found in the peripheries. There are some ferro-concrete structures belonging to the prosperous merchants and modern flats of the wealthy residents standing side by side with traditional structures but big houses even in the country side appear not to have been reached by modern influence. In contrast to the indigenous parts of the town, civil lines, labour colonies are planned and they have been constructed to serve definite purpose. They are characterized by rectangular layout of streets. In civil lines all the buildings are brick – built generally constructed in western style with some modification such as the addition of verandah and courtyard so as to suit the local climate. The density of population is low an compared to the old section of the town with extensive lanes, shady avenues, flatish skyline looked something like the spire of a church or high buildings. The civil lines present a distinctly modern appearance. In Contai municipality could not create any housing facilities are giving to the Harijan employees. Excepting that there are some govt. quarters are constructed for govt. employees. Due to growth of population there is high demand for housing complexes. In Contai town some words are belong to slums condition. There, the housing pattern are mostly tile- roofing from. These busties have insanitary houses and they stand in contrast to the well-built brick houses. Adequate quarters must be built in the near future by the management of different factories and government to house all employees of the city, but it is done, the busties should maintain sanitary norms. Busti is essentially a rural mode of living. The workers of Contai are mostly rural in origin and

therefore, they do not feel incongenial in “busti-life”. As long as rural character of busties are maintained it is not unhealthy.

Build and Architecture – The buildings and their architecture in Contai are products of the twentieth century. Hence the entire pattern is modern. Minarates and domes are not observed in Contai except in the mosques; temples, dargha and churches. But even the fifty years life of the city demonstrates some significant changes in the house types. Besides Gandhi road there are observed many old buildings which are tiled entirely or the front Verandah is tiled, but they are invariably devoid of descent appearance. On the other hand, newly built buildings of Chowrangi, Netaji Para, are not only built by cement and concrete but out verandah is descent.

There are large areas of employees built quarters and bungalow which are one colour. It is mostly the light yellow which is the result of white washing. The pipe line flats and houses are yellowish in colour and it is made up of tiles. The new bungalows have red coloured roofs and yellow coloured walls.

FUNCTIONAL IMPACT ON CONTAI TOWN :- The development of various is also highly governed by the patterns and the location of roads. The formation of CBD is generally found at the places where wide open roads from various directions coverage and provide highest accessibility. In Contai the Chowrangi is the CBD place because Gandhi road, Digha road and Deshpran sarani meet together from various directions.

Other functions develop alongside the C B D according to their ability to bid completely for the land. There usually emerges in any sizeable city. Several types of functional zones with characteristic landscape, such as residential, business, Industrial, administrative, educational and recreational, all varying in strength and intensity according to the site and size of the town. It is necessary to remark here that these zones, however, distinct they may look on the map, are complicated in detail, and may involve other functions also. With the development of trade, commerce and peaceful environments the mercantile community settled in the core town. The religious administrative areas, residential areas all are attracted towards the hub, taking advantages of the local facilities. So the old core of the town maintain a synthetic land-user pattern where all functions are combined in a single compact site. The wholesale markets develop in close associations of transport channels along the highways, the wholesale business area of Contai town (super market) as a grain market in Contai, which feeds the whole town and surrounding region.

In Contai town commercial, industrial, residential, institutional, services and public utility functions covered extensive locations. With the result the Contai town developed recognizable functional topography. The administrative and educational zones with other public utility centers, produced a change in the Contai town morphology by occupying larger open spaces in new virgin areas. In Contai town marshy lands occupies more space in all the 18 wards. The civil lines, court cannot escape from the eyes of the casual observer. Thus new open surroundings of residential, commercial and similar other functions were added more firmly to the landscape. Industrial which are found in ward no. – 10, Athilaguri mouza occupied only 0.30 acre of the total land. The administrative sections are found in core center. Actually these new developments introduced an altogether new element in the cultural fabric of the town.

The morphological set-up of the function varies because it is the outcome of human creative instincts projected through the total setting of resources and cultures within the limits of time and space. It produces a complicated picture.

The city structure, the evolutionary and the resultant, cumulative morphological set-up bring out, in general, three distinct parts of different form and characteristics in the towns – indigenous, anglicized and the newly developed planned areas. The development of post independence period completely differ from the above two so far as the layout plan, the house plan, functional segregation and set – up for non-use of land. Though the many parts of area are full of marshy land but they are not usable.

In modern comfortably designed buildings a healthy surrounding can be seen in many parts of Contai town. These newly planned sections have developed during the last thirty years.

INDIGENOUS PARTS OF CONTAI TOWN :- We can discuss this to divide it into two parts –

- (i) **The business section** :- The business section of Contai town are very clumsy and congested developments of two storeyed buildings along any major roadsides. The Digha road may be taken as an example of the major road. This place comprises of establishments with different types of functions occurring side by side. Establishment with general merchandise stationary, various types of fabrics, cinema houses, restaurants, medical shops etc, are found in this area. All these establishments are in the ground floor of roadside building which have very compact nature. Upper stories are occupied by the office and trading companies. The establishments just behind the roadside buildings are narrow and crooked lanes, and frequent small shops of variable nature. The movement of vehicles on the streets in this place is very difficult.

- (ii) **Other than business section** :- It is mainly covered by the residential buildings. In Contai the buildings are generally single and double storied and the streets are comparatively boarder, this types of building can be found in Vidyasagar Sarani, Khudiram Sarani, Raghunath sarani etc. The inter-space between the building are also found. The maidan and the open space found very common in Karkuli and Monohar chak. Uttar Darua, Dharmadasagar, Athilaguri this place having chiefly residential quarters also possess small and markets of retail nature. The board gauge “Kathi Railway Line” is also fund here.

THE ANGLICIZED PARTS OF CONTAI TOWN :- The anglicised parts of Contai town have wide roads individual residential bungalows with sufficient area, well-defined functional establishments and tree-lined roadside. It is consist of at present mainly by the government servants and other skilled groups.

Civil line :- Consist mainly of residential quarters for high class professional. Many residential quarters are found along the Deshpran road, we cantake it for example. The bungalows are generally single storeyed with a large open ground in front. The walls of the house are generally thick and windows are large. The houses most commonly comprise of tiles roof. Large verandah with pillars running all round. The roads are well-paved board. Courts central jails, transport office, B.L.R.O Office administrative office are situated here. The big parks, officers residential bungalows now have private residential buildings, labour colonies and other uses Hostels, Schools, Cinema hall, play ground, Sishu Uddan are the other significant functional uses of this area.

Railway colonies: - In Contai there is only one railway station, that is Kanthis railway station. It is not a good train, only for passenger train. The trains comes here twice daily. It is a broad gauge railway station. The distinctive feature of railway colonies are the uniform grid of streets and similar styles rows of brick houses, graded and rented, according to the pay-scale and status of the railway employees, The vast railway yards, extensive plants for the manufacture of railway extensive plants for the manufacture of railway materials etc. Are the marked features in the morphology of railway colonies of Contai town.

Newly planned areas: - Newly planned developments have taken place towards the north potion of the town. Government planned to establish a railway station in the northern portion. The railway line will be established through the ward no. 1, 15. Near the bus terminus, municipality built a market complex which construction is going on. It will be storeyed market complex. The market complex having many rooms. Which will be use for many business purpose. The residential neighbourhoods, labour colonies have developed on planning principles. The street pattern of these areas are quite scientific being rectangular.

The business areas educational areas recently developed in the last thirty years. Building, this types and designs are most modernized.

Morphological zones of Contai town :- The cities are functionally very complex and this complexity goes on increasing as new function are added with the economic growth which sets in constantly changing linkage patterns between various types of land-use. It is not a surprising feature that business. Industries and other functional zones vary in area from one city to another, according to the nature, size and functional character of the cities. In Contai town the morphological zones are also present. Residential areas, business areas, administrative areas, recreational religious areas, public and semi public areas, vacant and agricultural areas are covered whole the area.

Table No -1

Land use pattern of contai town in acre and percentage-

Land use pattern	Land/ acre	Land (in %)
1. Residential areas	759.82	24.31
2. Commercial areas	30.27	0.97
3. Administrative areas	4.91	0.16
4. Recreational areas	10.79	0.35
5. Public and semi public areas	272.01	8.70
6. Religious areas	12.37	0.40
7. Industrial areas	0.30	5.60
8. Transport areas	155.2	4.97
9. Vacant areas	1773.14	45.02
10. Agricultural areas	106.64	3.41
Total	3125.45	

Source- B.L.R.O . Office of Contai town

From the above we can say that in Contai town the vacant areas are found more. Contai located beside Digha is a sea beach of Bay of Bengal. For the relief of contai town, sand dunes and marshy land are found in many parts of the town. So the huge amount of vacant land found here. Only in Athialiguri (Ward no- 10) there is found one industry.

The cultivation of cashew nut are found more in contai. So the cashew industries are also there which are associated with cashew prod.

Morphological units :-

1) Residential zone – The intermingling of residential areas with the business and industries has been a common feature in our cities. The back side and the upper storeys of the business and household and small scale industrial sectors are mostly used for dwellings purposes and some for office purposes. The old part of the city is congested dirt, ill-drainage and the unhygienic residence. The slums and the blighted areas, as the worst component of urban dwellings, have hardly left untouched any city.

Among the residential zone the most important is the residential colony of contain town. All houses are modern and metalled. The other residential areas are along the roads and railway stations. Moderns houses are being constructed along these roads. Away from the road the land is still devoted to agriculture. All the administrative offices have been set-up along the Gandhi road. In the C B D area the high rised buildings with shopping complex are found. Those ward which are belong to slums areas, low class residence are found there. Away the CBD the middle class reditial areas are lying.

The notable shift in location of different classes of residential areas in recent years is mostly transportation oriented. The general change is found with the high class residential quarters. Middle class residential areas lying towards the outer margins, are still close to the old developed parts. The low class cannot afford to shift outside but there are some examples of shifting within this zone as well as on its periphery.

The residential areas in contai town is 759.82 acre (24.31%) of total land area. Its show less percentage of residential areas although having high populated. And the other reason is a good fraction of land is occupied by business, industry and semi public functions.

Table No-2

Land under residential uses

Ward no.	Land/ acre	% of land
1	39.01	5.13
2	26.6	15.10
3	114.73	3.17

4	24.1	3.12
5	23.62	7.07
6	53.75	9.32
7	70.82	1.75
8	13.31	7.54
9	57.26	6.77
10	51.46	4.36
11	33.11	2.90
12	22.02	2.90
13	22.06	7.76
14	58.99	7.49
15	56.91	3.34
16	25.35	7.03
17	53.41	1.75
18	13.31	

Source –B.L.R.O office of contai town

From the above table we can say that the ward no -3 having high residential areas and ward no – 8, 18 having low residential areas.

2) Commercial zone- It will be benefiting approach to assess the use of land for now residential purpose, because such class constitutes about 62% of total developed area of the Indian cities among which the business zone is of the prime importance. Beside this business and commercial areas, some new markets on a bit improved pattern were development which is away from the congested center of the city.

The modern planned business areas are well defined and have definite characters. The classified, planned layout and housing certainly produce a striking difference in the markets observed in the rest two areas.

In contai the commercial areas occupied 30.27 acre (0.97%) of the total land area. Major portion of the commercial land is inside the city walls, which is having more number of shops as compared to the area outside the city wall. New business center has developed near the bus-stand. It is due to the advantage of transportation facilities. Retail shops are also found in the residential colony. The shops are opened along the road side. From the CBD center, many roads going different part and all the road side covered with retail shops. In ward no-3 (Uttar Darua) the business areas occupied high percentage 19.56 than

ward no-17 (16.15%). In Uttar Darua the populated % are also high and it is the main reason for spreading commercial areas. In ward no-1 there business is situated in periphery area. Here no. of shops are less and people provided by weekly market people depends on outgoing markets.

The most important business is dry fish business. In many areas people depends on fish culture. They made pond and started fishing. Sea fish and sea food are the main commodity which the harbour handles here. They made dry fish and soled them in different parts of the town. In contia most of the people are engaged in this business

Table no-3

Land under Commercial zone

Word no.	Land /area	% of land
1	0.20	0.66
2	0.46	1.52
3	5.92	19.56
4	1.8	5.95
5	0.25	0.83
6	1.12	3.70
7	2.17	7.17
8	-	-
9	2.25	7.43
10	2.8	9.25
11	3.08	10.18
12	0.27	0.89
13	2.43	8.03
14	0.97	3.20
15	-	-
16	1.66	5.48
17	4.89	16.15
18	-	-
Total	30.27	100

Source – B.L.R.O office of contai town .

3) Administrative zone:- Administrative areas are all government lands Administrative areas are associated with post office , bank, municipality, collectorate , office of the district register , District land and land reforms office, jail , other offices are all located in different parts of town offices situated in the office complex . In Hatabari and sub-division Kumarpur the administrative offices are situated. Administrative areas in sub-division Kumarpur 4.66 acre (94.91%) and in Hatabari 0.25 acre (5.09%).

Land under administrative use

<u>Ward no.</u>	<u>land/ acre</u>	<u>% of land</u>
9	4.66	94.91
11	0.25	5.09

4) Recreational zone:-Parks and playgrounds are general valued as the lungs of a city providing facilities for recreation and games . These open spaces in addition to the some of the recreational buildings such cinemas, clubs and theatres , infect , do not from any particular zone in a city , certainly if any they are scattered in an improper and unbalanced manner. The old congested areas due to lack of foresight generally do not have greater facility. As an unhappy consequence parks and open spaces are not only inadequate but poorly distributed also.

In Contai the recreational areas occupied 10.79 acre (0.35%) . Sub division Kumarpur Karkuli Padmapukhuria. Dhandighi having more recreational places than other. Here recreational areas shares small space of the town because areas under parks are freely utilized by the general public hence, even a small percentage satisfies the need of larger people. All these towns are centers which have got busy routine of life and hence greater facilities of entertainment in the form of open spaces.

Table no -4

Land under recreational use

Ward no.	Land /acre	% of land
1	2.45	22.71
2	0.04	0.37
9	2.09	19.37
13	2.00	18.54
15	0.05	0.46

16	2.99	27.71
17	0.05	0.46
18	1.12	10.38

Source- B.L.R.O Office of contain town

5) Zone of public and semipublic uses:-

The specific feature of establishment, such as educational, medical, churches, temples, mosques, etc. classified as public and semipublic properly is quite different in morphological pattern from that of other functions. This zone produces a different cultural world indeed in the indigenous soil but not rooted to it.

It can be emphasized here that this zone very in areas and facilities. The pattern of percentage semi public uses does not show any significant correlation with the population size of the cities. Though a very rough negative correlation can be seen in the diagram which implies that the increase in population size tends to bring the decrease in public and semi-public areas.

In contain the public and semipublic areas are very high. In ward no – 9 and 13 these data are not available. Excepting 2 wards all wards having comparatively same percentage.

Table No-5

Land under public and semipublic use

Word no-	Land /acre	% of land
1	24.79	9.11
2	14.26	5.24
3	68.60	25.22
4	9.69	3.56
5	14.89	5.47
6	12.56	4.62
7	25.51	9.38
8	2.7	0.99
10	17.93	6.60
11	5.65	2.08

12	11.14	4.10
14	23.30	8.59
15	11.10	4.08
16	4.39	1.61
17	22.69	8.34
18	2.75	1.01
Total	272.01	100

Source:-B.L.R.O office contain town

6) Religious Zone:- Religious areas are associated with temple, masjid ,dargha , pirdargha , churches ,act. If any place is famous for religious fact then it attracted people lot than the other parts. In contia there are many sitala mandir. In slums area where peoples are mostly Muslims masjid, dargha are found there more. Contia is famous for Kapalkundala minder . In many places these mandirare located . Here the famous writer Banking Chandra Chattopadhaya Wrote his famous novel “Kapal Kundala “ . The local people said that the original mandir of Papal kundala can be found in the way of petua that

Table No – 6

Land under religious use

Word no.	Land / acre	% of land
1	0.09	0.73
2	0.09	0.73
3	3.16	25.55
4	0.15	1.21
5	0.34	2.75
6	0.65	5.25
7	1.41	11.40
8	1.28	10.35
9	2.2	17.78
10	0.35	2.83
11	-	-
12	0.83	6.71
13	0.08	0.65

14	0.18	1.46
15	0.17	1.37
16	0.16	1.29
17	1.23	9.94
18	-	-
Total	12.37	100

Source – B.L.R.O. office of contain town

7) Industrial Zone - Among economic activities industries play most important role infirming and changing the morphological pattern of an urban center. The light industry with its local sphere of influence mostly finds it location in the central part of the city.

Among the present day the problems the most challenging and costliest one is that some inductions of the early developed industries are unhealthy and geographically unsuitable for the present day. The contain municipality free from these problem. Here the industry is agro based. The production is Kashewnti . In ward no- 10, there is found one industry. Thought there are some cottage industry which are not vary significant.

Table No- 7

Land under industry use

Ward no.	Land/acre	% of Land
10	0.30	100

8) Transportation Zone- For the development of any area transport is very important. Those areas get more facility of transport it develops. In contain the transport facilities are goods. It connected by metalled road to Kolkata, which is the main and only road connection and the main artery of the economic activities in this region. The bus terminus is located near the border side of the municipality ward. There is a bye pass connecting both the Digha and Machida. The Digha Contia Road is connected with Shankarpur region, where the fishing harbor is newly constructed and it is the only road connecting shankarpur with the rest of the area.

Apart from road connection there is a plan for connecting railway line in north -eastern portion and in this respect land for railway construction was reserved and other infrastructure such as railway station and quarters were constructed but not an inch of railway line exists there.

The total land for transportation areas are 155.2 acre (4.97%). In Uttar Darua the transport facilities are good than the other wards.

Table No-8

Land under transport use

Ward no.	Land /acre	% of land
1	5.84	3.76
2	5.05	3.25
3	27.99	18.03
4	3.61	2.33
5	4.14	2.67
6	10.57	6.81
7	8.78	5.66
8	3.8	2.45
9	5.66	3.65
10	9.31	6.00
11	5.62	3.62
12	3.6	2.32
13	4.21	2.71
14	16.11	10.38
15	12	7.73
16	13.47	8.68
17	11.64	7.5
18	3.8	2.45
Total	155.2	100

9) **Agricultural Zone** - In contain the agriculture areas are covered 106.64 acre (3.41%) of the total land. Agriculture are mainly found in the periphery zone. Most of the places are cultivated cashewnut. The land is suitable for cultivation of cashewnut and well supplied by irrigational water. Some plantation agriculture is also found in this area. Some area are planted with bamboo garden, fruit gardens.

Table No – 9

Land under agriculture use

Word No .	Land/ acre	% of land
1	0.72	0.68
2	0.14	0.13
3	5.16	4.84
4	14.42	13.52
5	3.91	3.67
6	10.93	10.25
7	2.43	2.28
8	3.88	3.64
9	1.83	1.72
10	2.87	2.69`
11	0.23	2.69
12	1.82	1.71
13	5.07	4.75
14	0.21	0.20
15	19.98	18.74
16	0.48	0.45
17	28.68	26.89
18	3.88	3.64
Total	106.64	100

Source :- B.L.R.o. office , contai town

10) Vacant zones - Here the vacant places occupies more 1773.14 acre (54.02%) of the total land area. Sand dune and marshy lands are found more in this town. In ward no -7 vacant areas are found more , then ward no – 7 and ward no -1 vacant areas are very less found in ward no – 11 (0.28%). For the relief feature most of the land are not unusable for any purpose.

Table No- 10

Land under vacant area

Ward no.	Land / acre	% of land
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1	228.04	12.86
2	76.47	4.31
3	84.84	4.78
4	46.43	2.62
5	72.27	4.08
6	171.76	9.69
7	256.18	14.45
8	79.58	4.49
9	14.18	0.80
10	22.81	1.29
11	5.05	0.28
12	60.79	3.43
13	91.71	5.17
14	187.9	10.60
15	69.67	3.82
16	20.58	1.16
17	230.83	13.02
18	56.06	3.16
Total	1773.14	100

Source – B.L.R. O office of Contain town

Table No-11

Word – wise Land use pattern of conitias town (%)

Word no.	Residential areas	Commercial areas	Administrative areas	Recreational areas	Public and semi public areas	Religious areas	Industrial areas	Transportation areas	Vactan area	Agricultural areas	Total
1	12.95	0.07		0.81	8.23	0.03		1.94	75.73	0.24	100

2	21.61	0.37		0.03	11.58	0.07		4.10	62.12	0.11	“
3	36.96	1.91			22.10	1.02		9.02	27.33	1.66	“
4	24.05	1.80			9.67	0.15		3.60	46.44	14.39	“
5	19.78	0.21			12.47	0.28		3.47	60.52	3.27	“
6	20.57	0.43			4.81	0.25		4.04	65.72	4.18	“
7	19.28	0.53			6.94	0.38		2.39	69.75	0.66	“
8	12.73				2.58	1.22		3.63	76.12	3.71	“
9	63.53	2.50	5.17	2.32		2.44		6.28	15.73	2.03	“
10	47.72	2.60			16.63	0.32	0.29	8.63	21.15	2.66	“
11	62.5	5.81	0.47		10.66			10.61	9.51	0.43	“
12	21.92	0.27			11.09	0.83		3.58	60.50	1.81	“
13	17.29	1.90		1.57		0.06		3.30	71.90	3.97	“
14	20.50	0.34			8.12	0.10		5.60	65.31	0.07	“
15	33.90			0.03	6.61	0.23		7.15	40.31	11.90	“
16	36.70	2.40		4.33	6.35	0.23		19.50	29.79	0.69	“
17	36.70	2.40		4.33	6.35			19.50	29.79	0.69	“
18	16.45			1.38	3.40			4.72	69.28	4.79	“

Source- B.L.R.O office of Contain town.

CONCLUSION

Morphology of Indian cities forms a complex and complicated aspect of the urban geography. For the improvement and better facture Indian cities await crystal cut analysis of their internal aspect and problems. A subtle remark will be sufficient here that the morphology of cities is never cities is never static. It is always dynamic. So, we can say that morphology of Contain town will be changed in future. Many changes will be take place and development will be also established in this town. It can be further emphasized that at the modern stage of planning, the internal appearance of the town is in the operation

theater, but it will have the supremacy of its original shape and colour under changed grab. The peripheries and fringe areas are expected to have stormy change in their morphology and look, while the internal changes will probably enjoy normal and rather slower course of cycle.

REFERENCES :-

- District census hand book -1991, 2001, East Midnapore , West Bangle, India .
- Mandal. R.B (2000) – Urban Geography, A textbook, Concept publishing Company, New Delhi, India, PP-86-104.
- Detail Project report of contain Municipality, East Midnapore , West Bangle, India .
- Taneja. Kusum Lata. “Morphology of Indian cities” Varanasi: - National geographic society of India, 1971.
- Misra , R.P, ed . Million cities of India. New Delhi : Vikas , 1978